

Portfolio optimization modeling through real time reports and analytics.

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Abstract

The volume and complexity of information in enterprises are increasing at the same time that businesses are looking to take advantage of that information to gain a competitive edge. Companies look for a compromise between the timeliness of information and cost impact. In this competitive environment, there is an increased need for automatic decision-making. These decisions are realized through real-time business intelligence (RTBI), real-time reporting and real time analytics (RTA). Giving the fact that bank industries are rich with data and the decisions are time-sensitive, real time solutions will help improve customer experiences and operational productivity. This paper will give an overview on the importance and challenges of real-time reporting, RTBI and RTA. In addition to the analysis in this area, the article presents a portfolio modeling optimization for banking through real time analytics. This model will reduce time consumption, improve customer performance, and data quality.

Keywords: Real Time Reports, Real Time BI, Real Time Analytics, cross selling

INTRODUCTION

Data warehousing has been one of the key implementation practices which was followed in many industries. With the rapid change in customer buying habits and frequently changing markets every business needs more insight into all the available data that is in the database. A successful company needs to take better business decision based on the most recent data. Hence if we have a real time reporting it can provide the business insights based on the real time data available and it will definitely help the organizations to understand the business in real time and take better decision on the fly.

A real-time reporting system is based on a real-time ETL and a real-time data warehouse. Also known as active data warehouse, real time data warehouse is a combination of fast technologies and fast business processes. One of the most challenging parts of building any data warehouse is the process of extracting, transforming and loading (ETL) the data from the sources. Talking about real-time data warehouse, additional challenges like data modeling, scalability, OLAP (Online Analytics Processing), query tools and cost implementation. However considering the problems of the traditional approach real time DW is a new technology that responds to business demands. Traditional business reporting is built and packaged in batches. It doesn't allow for high velocity or a high volume data. It also has significant performance problems with large data sets. Most traditional business intelligence expects arbitrary query extracts before users can visualize data. Getting that initial query and dealing with the changes can take forever and frustrate users. Although IT experts try to address this issue by extracting data periodically from big data systems and transforming it in batches such that it becomes more consumable, the approach is not continuous. Today, more types of data are springing up, therefore, it's important to have more resources to manage data transformation. Alternatives, such as reporting directly against Online Transactional Processing systems, real time BI tools or real time reporting which are called real time analytics, have been studied and proposed over the years.

1. REPORTING IN A TRADITIONAL DATA WAREHOUSE SYSTEM

The goal of any data warehouse system is to provide analytic reporting based on the historical data available in the cubes that were loaded from multiple source systems. A source system can be of any kind like Customer relationship Management (CRM), Excel based flat files, Logistics and finance application data. An organization which has many legacy systems will use a data warehouse system to consolidate the data from multiple source and cleanse the data within the business intelligence system and store the data with the business intelligence systems in a common format.[1]

In our case study the main focus is on CRM system which is a system to store the various transaction data related to customer relation management. The data from the CRM system can be used to produce analytical reports and help to understand the customer behavior.

In the traditionally data warehouse data consolidation layer captures data from multiple source systems and integrates it into a single persistent target data store, such as a data warehouse. Target data-stores contain high-latency data that is typically used for strategic and tactical BI processing. These stores are built using batch data integration applications that pull data from the source systems at predefined scheduled intervals. In our case Real Time Data Warehouse is the target data store. During data consolidation, data-transform techniques may be used to transform and cleanse the data. As data changes occur in source systems, change data capture techniques may be used to stream the updates to a target data store. [2] From what we said above it seems that traditional DW has some limitations. Precisely the reports provided from this structure are mostly based on historical data. But the current business markets are changing, the customer habits are changing henceforth a business need to have analytical report that provides data about the business in right time. Therefore the right decision makes a business more effective, so many environments are using the approach to real time reporting, and remember *the value of data diminishes over time*.

2. Previous work on Real Time BI

Real-time report is a business intelligence feature, the process of providing appropriate information about business operations as they occur, with minimum latency.

Sometimes right-time is a better term to use than real time. This because “Right-time implies that different business situations and events require different response or action times. When planning a right-time processing environment, it is important to match technology requirements to the actual action times required by the business - some situations require close to a real-time action, whereas with others, a delay of a few minutes or hours is acceptable.” [3]

All business intelligence systems have some latency, but the goal is to minimize the time from the business event happening and maximizing the value of business. So if we consider the **total time between the happening of the event business and the distribution of information to the end user**, it can be divide into three different components, which concern “Fig 1”:

1. **Data (data latency)**- represents the preparatory phase in which they are acquired, transformed memorized and made available for BI analysis. Data Latency also depends on the context of the business where it is applied, for example in medicine or monitoring systems, it is a matter of milliseconds. While for the banking systems which we will treat below, a higher latency data can be tolerated. Besides data latency, data unavailability is another impediment to efficient real-time business intelligence.
2. **Analysis (analysis latency)** - is consequential to the time necessary to analyze process and present data.
3. **Decisions (decision latency)** - is the final stage in which, in front of information extracted and knowledge of the business, are decided the actions to be taken.

The sum of this three latency periods is called the **BI reaction time** which represents the goal of real-time BI techniques that are called to minimize it. The more time is needed to process the cognitive event the greater is the loss of information.

Figure 1. RTBI latency [4]

Giving the fact that business are dependent on real-time business intelligence, the unavailability of this intelligence due to a failed system could stop the operations. Great availability of the real-time business intelligence services is important. RTBI provides almost the same functionality as the traditional business intelligence, but operates on data that is extracted from operational data sources with zero latency, and provides means to spread actions back into business processes in real-time [5]. While traditional business intelligence gifts historical data for manual analysis, real-time business intelligence relates current business events with historical patterns to detect problems or opportunities automatically. This automated analysis capability enables corrective actions to be initiated and or business rules to be adjusted to optimize business processes [6]. Obviously real-time business intelligence system is based on a real-time ETL and a real-time data warehouse. Also known as active data warehouse, real-time data warehouse is a combination of fast technologies and fast-paced business processes. One of the most challenging parts of building any data warehouse is the process of extracting, transforming and loading (ETL) the data from the sources. Talking about real-time data warehouse, additional challenges are being introduced. The traditional ETL process involves downtime of the data warehouse while data is loading, but when we are performing real-time data loading, there cannot be any downtime of the system. For some applications, increasing the frequency of the current data load may be a solution. Nearby the raised costs, real-time data warehouse brings up some important issues like data modeling, scalability and query [7]. Storing real-time data along with the historical data, in the same fact tables, can be a good idea from the data modeling perspective because a real-time data warehouse is modeled just like a traditional data warehouse. Part of BI are also real time report or query analysis which we will treat in our model through real time data warehouses processes.

3. The demand for real time reporting

In contrast to the traditional data warehouses, which provide a historical snapshot of data at a past point in time, real-time data warehouses allow decision makers to analyze current transactions and trends as they occur. The demand for the migration from a traditional to real-time data warehousing derivate from the need for decision makers to incorporate current data from multiple data sources into the decision making. Real time data warehousing is faster, allowing the business to make quicker informative decisions based on the real-time and historical data present in the data warehouse. Businesses find this extremely attractive because the quicker they are able to respond to certain trends in the market the more successful they will be. The business strategy is always based on the analytical reports or the business data available. In the era of the historical system reporting if the organization were able to understand the customer behavior in the past, now to make the business effective the organizations have to understand the business and customer market in real time that is while the business in running. For example an retail store should be able to get the information of which products is currently moving better and this can be achieved only if the organization have business intelligence systems that provide real time data. The movement to real-time is the latest development in

business intelligence (BI) and data warehousing. Real-time data warehousing provides the data that is required to implement real time reporting. By moving to real-time, companies can use business analytics to affect current decision-making and business processes. This capability is especially important for customer-facing applications. The purpose of real-time analytics is to increase revenues, decrease costs, and improve supply cable management. Companies that successfully implement real-time reporting or real-time BI can dramatically improve their profitability, of course all this is achieved at extra cost in infrastructure.

3.1 Real time reporting and analytics in banking

In an increasingly competitive world financial organizations such as banks, credit unions, insurance companies and etc. must focus on data analytics, and moreover, investments in this ground are necessary in order to maintain a competitive edge. For this in upcoming year's big data and analytics are considered as the top investment priority of banks. The main reason for this investment focus is to better understand and target customers. For the uninitiated, data analytics is the process that focuses on the processing and performing statistical analysis on existing business data to describe, predict, and improve business performance. There are different areas where real time analytics has the max effect: consumer and marketing analytics, risk, fraud and portfolio optimization modeling.

In today's data-driven world it is not so simple, and by using traditional methods it is even impossible to store and process the massive amount of data. Several studies have been done on the impact that a real-time decision-making has on some banking functionalities, based on the findings shown in the Accenture Banking Technology Vision 2019 [9]:

- 87% of banking executives have acknowledged that the union between customization and real-time will set the tone of competitive advantage in the future.
- The same report states that only 38% of these banking executives have seen their organizations prioritizing customization.
- Further, only 9% are focusing on on-demand delivery.

Based on these above indicators, banks should think as soon as possible of solutions based on real time reports or analytics to gain a competitive advantage. For this we can rely on new technologies as real time data warehouse gives an opportunity to do real-time analysis with minimum data loss, which means also using real time analytics such as real time reporting to make informed decisions while events are happening. As we now traditionally reporting is the basic version of analytics solution that focused on giving information about a current situation. Whereas real time reporting is recording and reporting an event at the moment it occurs. In the past, most companies gathered their financial data reports during quarterly or monthly intervals, but with real time reporting, companies can now view and access their financial and other data right as it is happening – in real time!

4. Portfolio optimization modeling

In general a real time reporting needs the data to be fetched from the source system in real time. When the transaction is completed in the system it should be made available in the business intelligence system. To build a real-time reporting system you need to build a good plan regarding what kind of data should be retrieved, who is allowed to retrieve it and what's the appropriate dimensional model to use. We will introduce a real-time reporting model as "Fig 2" for banks related to the costumer portfolio. This model proposes increasing sales through the cross-selling technique based on real time analytics. The system will generate a real time alert using real time data processing. Alerts are essential for indicating a specific action to be taken from the end user perspective. In business intelligence systems for a report when there is a specific alert maintained for a set of data the real time analytical reports upon finding the specific value will show alerts to the report generated by end user.

Figure 2. Flow chart for the proposed model

The most complex task in RTDW is ETL process. The main challenges of ETL lie on performance degradation at data sources during data extraction, and on performing complex operations on large data volumes in short time frames. The ideal solution has two conflicting goals: (1) cause no impact on data sources and (2) process data in real-time as they are generated or updated. Ideal solutions should handle high-volume input data rates and perform complex operations in short time frames while extracting data with no operational overhead [8].

In our case study all data are extracted in real time from the source which is a traditional database through constantly updated job “Fig 3”. Then the data are held in star schemas in the target Real Time DW (tested on 500Mb), from which data will be taken to SQL Server Reporting.

Figure 3. Real-Time architecture for the proposed model

The tables in a star-schema are divided into two categories: facts and dimensions. Every star-schema has a single fact table and one or more dimensions:

- *Fact tables* contain individual rows for every occurrence of a fact in the source system. Fact tables contain columns called measures. It is these columns that are aggregated to calculate key performance indicators (KPIs).
- *Dimension tables* are used to share the facts in different ways. For example, the star schema above “Fig 3” would allow users to share the financial fact by the customer on the 6 dimensions linked to it.

The extract processes are extracting operational data and performing some transformation activities. A separate extract process is used for every distinct fact and dimension.

Figure 3. Real time Reporting Star Schema

By doing an analysis together with the business department in the bank we have identified 6 different types of products that can be sold through real time analytics improving customer portfolio. Based on the customer data as well as the actions he performs in the bank we manage to analyze and identify these Alert for Sale and in Real Time.

Product1	Offer E-banking
Product2	Offer Payroll account
Product3	Offer Fixed Time Deposit
Product4	Offer Debit Card
Product5	Offer Junior Deposit
Product6	Offer Consumer Loan

We enter the client ID number and after clicking View Report the report is executed on the target RTDW, through query processing. Which is presented in the previous works [10]. Once the report is generated, depending on the customer data that match the definded conditions, will be suggested through a real time alert the sale of one of the above products "Fig 3". Based on what we said above, the client can change the personal data while performing a banking service and they will be reflected in the RTDW. Next RTDW will display the changes in the final report, suggesting sales with the current user data.

Figure 4. Cross Selling technique through real-time report

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have dealt with real-time BI and real-time reports and real time analytics, both of them provide insights into the business operation and future decisions, but it comes down to the differences into how they do it and what information exactly do they provide. In my opinion RTBI is needed to understand the business while RTA are needed to change the business, also RTBI use multiple source of data whereas RTA use specific set of data. Nevertheless over the years these two approaches are being used more and more to make effective business decisions and to provide business insights in real-time. Furthermore, real-time business intelligence already has a massive impact on revenue globally. With access to key performance indicators and advanced analytics models, managers and executives can get a clearer picture of their business, make better decisions and diagnose problems properly. Therefore, in this paper, we have paid attention to real-time reporting by proposing a model based on the real-time data warehouse for the bank industry. This model will have a significant impact on customer portfolio, deriving. Apart from what we said above, generally, real-time reporting brings flexibility, as many real-time reporting solutions allow decision-makers to design reports and customize data displayed to meet their specific needs, and accuracy, as the probability of errors is reduced.

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